

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES

Figure S1. Univariate divergence of environmental conditions for all environmental variables and their best-fit models.

species + range + (species x range)

species + range

range

Figure S2. Test of niche equivalency, similarity, and expansion for (a) Red-crowned Parrots and (b) Lilac-crowned Parrots. The test of niche equivalency assesses whether the native and introduced niches are equal by comparing the observed niche overlap (red marker) to a null distribution created by pooling observations from the native and introduced ranges. The test of niche similarity compares the observed value of niche overlap (red marker) with a null distribution of overlap values created by comparison of the native range to random values drawn from the background of the introduced range.

Figure S3. Reciprocal species distribution models for each parrot species, separately projected onto the opposite native range. Habitat suitability from the (a) Red-crowned Parrot's native range was determined and projected onto the native Lilac-crowned Parrot range. Likewise, habitat suitability from the (b) Lilac-crowned Parrot's native range was determined and projected on the native Red-crowned Parrot range. Percentages and the total area of suitable habitat quantified by thresholding with the minimum training presence (MTP) are listed for each respective model. Maximum suitability scores for the (a) Red-crowned Parrot suitability in the Lilac-crowned Parrot range did not exceed 0.52 with a mean of 0.04 and for the (b) Lilac-crowned Parrot suitability in the Red-crowned Parrot range, the maximum did not exceed 0.94 with a mean of 0.02, showing little suitable habitat in the opposite ranges.

